

Airborne Millimeter-wave Radiometric Observations of Cirrus Clouds

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports the first radiometric measurements of cirrus clouds in the frequency range of 89-325 GHz from a high-altitude aircraft flight. The measurements are conducted with a Millimeter-wave Imaging Radiometer (MIR) on board the NASA ER-2 aircraft over a region in northern Oklahoma. Aboard the same aircraft are a cloud lidar system and a multichannel radiometer operating at the visible and infrared wavelengths. The instrument ensemble is well suited for identifying cirrus clouds. It is shown that the depressions in brightness temperatures associated with a few intense cirrus clouds occur at all frequency channels of the MIR. Estimates of total ice water path of the cirrus clouds are derived from comparisons of radiative transfer calculations and observed brightness depressions.

INTRODUCTION

Remote measurements of cirrus clouds have mostly been made in the visible and infrared regions of the electromagnetic wave spectrum [1]. Observations in the microwave and millimeter-wave regions were limited to ground-based radars [2]. At aircraft altitudes, there are measurements [3] over storms in which the brightness temperatures (T_b) in the frequency range of 90-220 GHz are ≤ 150 K. The modest decreases in T_b values at millimeter wavelengths expected from radiative transfer modeling of cirrus clouds [4], to the best of our knowledge, have not been observed and reported.

The following gives a brief description of MIR observations of cirrus clouds in the frequency range of 89-325 GHz [5]. The measurements were made over northern Oklahoma during the SUCCESS (SUBsonic aircraft: Contrail and Cloud Effects Special Study) mission of April-May 1996. The MIR was on board the NASA ER-2 aircraft, which was flown at an altitude of about 20 km and generally above the tops of most clouds. Data from two other instruments aboard the same aircraft, the Cloud Lidar System (CLS) and the MODIS (Moderate-resolution Imaging Spectrometer) Airborne Simulator (MAS), were used to help identify the presence of cirrus clouds. Three events of cirrus clouds are discussed in the following; they are among the most intense ones observed by the MIR during the mission.

OBSERVATIONS

The data reported in this paper were acquired on April 16, 1996 when the aircraft made 12 repeated passes over the same region in northern Oklahoma along the 36.6°N latitude line and between the two endpoints defined by the longitude lines of 95.9°W and 98.5°W. Figure 1 shows the backscatter profiles from the CLS and brightness temperatures $T(11 \mu\text{m})$ measured by the thermal infrared channel (11 μm) of the MAS over a straight 135-km path with two endpoints at geographic locations of (36.6°N, 97.5°W) and (36.6°N, 96.0°W). Four plots (A, B, C, and D) in the figure represent four consecutive measurements over the same path. The endpoint at (36.6°N, 97.5°W) always begins from the left side of each plot; thus, the time axes in plots (A) and (C) run from right to left. The top portion of each plot gives the heights of cloud layers and surface (~ 0 km) as detected by the CLS, which appear to be closely correlated to the $T(11 \mu\text{m})$ values measured by the MAS displayed in the bottom portion of the plot. In each of the plots (A), (B), and (C), there is a region where the values of $T(11 \mu\text{m})$ are < 250 K. In this region the CLS fails to observe the return signals from the surface; the region is covered with dense cirrus clouds that totally attenuate the lidar signals. In the fourth pass over the region between 1938-1949 UTC, shown in plot (D), $T(11 \mu\text{m})$ are ≥ 250 K, suggesting the presence of thin cirrus clouds only.

The corresponding variations of $T_b(\nu)$'s at frequency ν from the MIR for the same four consecutive passes are shown in Figure 2. Only the $T_b(\nu)$ values from six channels at 150, 220, 183.3 \pm 3, 183.3 \pm 7, 325 \pm 3, and 325 \pm 8 GHz are plotted in order to maintain the simplicity of the figure. The two horizontal dotted lines in each plot, at $T_b(\nu)$ values of 225 K and 250 K, provide a reference of $T_b(\nu)$ variations for the 183.3 GHz and 325 GHz channels, respectively. The two vertical dotted lines in plots (A), (B), and (C) identify the areas of dense cirrus where the CLS fails to observe signal return from the surface; in these areas a strong depression in $T_b(\nu)$'s are observed at all six channels. This depression in $T_b(\nu)$ displays a frequency dependence characteristic of wave scattering by ice particles: the higher the frequency of observations the stronger the $T_b(\nu)$ depression [4]. At the location of the strongest $T_b(\nu)$ depression in plot (C), for example, the changes in $T_b(\nu)$'s from their nominal values

Figure 1. Variations of lidar backscatter and 11 μm brightness from four ER-2 aircraft passes over the same region in northern Oklahoma.

Figure 2. Brightness temperature variations observed by the MIR at six frequencies from the same four ER-2 aircraft passes described in Figure 1

are about 12 K, 15 K, 30 K, and 35 K at frequency channels of 150, 183.3±7, 220 and 325±8 GHz respectively.

COMPARISON WITH CALCULATIONS

The measured brightness depressions, $\delta T_b(\nu)$'s, are compared with the results of radiative transfer calculations for estimation of cloud parameters as shown in Figure 3. Here the smooth curves adopted from Gasiewski [4] give the dependence of $\delta T_b(\nu)$ on cloud density at $\nu = 89, 166, 220,$ and 340 GHz. Notice that some of these calculations are not made at the exact frequencies as those of the MIR, but they are close enough for a valuable comparison with the MIR measurements. The values of $\delta T_b(\nu)$ at $\nu = 89, 150, 220,$ and 325 ± 8 GHz from areas of largest depressions in Figure 2, A, B and C, are plotted on the curves of 89, 166, 220 and 340 GHz in Figure 3.

The $\delta T_b(\nu)$ values observed at $\nu = 89, 220,$ and 325 GHz from the second and third passes, as represented by open and solid circles in Figure 3, give an estimated cloud density of about $0.05\text{-}0.06 \text{ g/m}^3$. The $\delta T_b(\nu)$ values at $\nu = 150, 220$ and 325 ± 8 GHz from the first pass around 1826 UTC give a cloud density of about 0.025 g/m^3 , which is much lower than $\sim 0.046 \text{ g/m}^3$ implied by the value of $\delta T_b(89)$. Clearly, calculated results do not match the observed values of $\delta T_b(89)$ for all three selected periods and yield cloud densities that are consistent with estimations at other frequencies. These discrepancies suggest the need of refining the radiative transfer calculations with realistic inputs of surface and atmospheric parameters.

CONCLUSION

Three cases of intense cirrus clouds observed by the MIR during the SUCCESS mission are presented in this paper. Although theoretical calculations [4] have shown cirrus clouds to have a measurable frequency response in the millimeter-wave region, the strong brightness depressions described in this paper provide the first conclusive evidence of cirrus cloud radiometric signatures in the frequency range of 89-325 GHz. The brightness depressions are found to be highly frequency dependent; for the three cases examined here, the brightness depression could be as large as 12 K at 150 GHz and 35 K at 325±8 GHz. The largest brightness depressions at several selected frequencies from each of the three cases are compared with the results of radiative transfer calculations for an estimation of cloud density. The estimated cloud density ranges from about 0.025 to 0.06 g/m^3 , which is equivalent to 50-120 g/m^2 of ice water path, based on a 2-km cloud layer assumed in the

Figure 3. Variations of measured and model-calculated brightness depressions with cloud density.

calculations. There are some discrepancies in the cloud density estimation from brightness depressions at different frequencies, which are likely due to the input of generalized surface and atmospheric parameters in the radiative transfer calculations. More realistic characterization of input parameters pertaining to the site environment are required to bring about a better agreement between measurements and calculations, and a more reliable estimation of ice water path.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. D. Spinhirne and W. D. Hart, "Cirrus structure and radiative parameters from airborne lidar and spectral radiometer observations: the 28 October 1986 FIRE study," *Mon Wea. Rev.*, **118**(11), 2329-2343, 1990.
- [2] S. Y. Matrosov, T. Uttal, J. B. Snider, and R. A. Kropfli, "Estimation of ice cloud parameters from ground-based infrared radiometer and radar measurements," *J. Geophys. Res.* **97**(D11), 11567-11574, 1992.
- [3] J. R. Wang, J. Y. Zhan, and P. Racette, "Storm-associated radiometric signatures in the frequency range of 89-220 GHz," *J. Atmos. Ocean. Tech.*, **14**(1), 13-31, 1997.
- [4] A. J. Gasiewski, "Numerical sensitivity analysis of passive EHF and SMMW channels to tropospheric water vapor, clouds and precipitation," *IEEE Trans. Geosci. Remote Sens.*, **30**(5), 859-870, 1992.
- [5] P. Racette, R. F. Adler, J. R. Wang, A. J. Gasiewski, D. M. Jackson, and D. Zacharias, "A millimeter-wave imaging radiometer for cloud, precipitation and atmospheric water vapor studies," *J. Atmos. Ocean. Tech.*, **13**(3), 610-619, 1997.